

EWS PROTOTYPE DESIGN: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK, SUBTASKS AND INTERACTION WITH THE PARTNERS

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A conceptual framework of the future early warning system (EWS) prototype for land degradation hazard mapping and prediction, which is currently being developed under the European EWALD project, is presented. The primary data source in the conceptual framework are the Earth observation data products, associated with the natural and anthropogenic drivers influence on land degradation processes.

An approach is proposed, which consists in translating heterogeneous (bio)physical indicators into an unified probabilistic form, followed by fusing ones into a joint hazard map. Forecasting is based on the hazard's time series analysis. Concomitantly with hazard mapping, a risk assessment of land degradation is carried out by socioeconomic geospatial modelling.

A preliminary decomposition of the whole worktask into subtasks with the assignment of responsible teams participating in the project for each subtask is proposed. A total of 12 subtasks are planned, in the execution of which all project's teams will be involved to different extents. Also, a detailed schedule of the subtasks' progress, including the final deliverable preparation, is drawn up.

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MULTIVARIATE RISK ASSESSMENT OF LAND DEGRADATION BY REMOTELY SENSED DATA

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In this paper, a novel method for the evaluation of land degradation in mountain-protected reserve areas based on remotely-sensed data. A risk map is developed based on this method for the investigated area. The risk is computed based on quantifying drivers of land degradation that can be estimated remotely. Terrain slope, vegetation cover, and surface soil moisture (SSM) are considered as these drivers in this paper. The risk value for developing a risk map is computed, which should be from one of the indicated classes (typically, the number of classes is from three to five). Therefore, the threshold for risk should be